

Northern-like Great Grey Shrike at Falsterbo, Sweden, in November 2020

Appendix – Molecular methods

DNA was isolated from a feather sample using the QIAGEN QIAamp DNA Micro Kit following the manufacturer's instructions, with 0.1 M dithiothreitol added during lysis. The mitochondrial cytochrome b (cytb) gene were amplified by PCR using primers L14993 and H16065 and PCR protocol as per Helbig & Seibold (1999).

Primers:

L14993: 5'-CCATCCAACATCTCAGCYTGATGAAAYTT-3'

H16065: 5'-GGAGTCTTCAGTTTTTGGTTTACAAGAC-3'

PCR Protocol:

PCRs were performed in 25 µl reactions, using 2 µl DNA, 5 µl primer mix, 5 µl MyFi Reaction Buffer and 0.5 µl MyFi DNA polymerase (Meridian Bioscience) and 12.5 µl ddH₂O.

Initial denaturation 2.5 mins at 94°C, followed by 32 cycles of 30s at 93°C, 30s at 45°C and 2 mins at 72°C, before a final extension of 10 mins at 72°C.

PCR products were gel purified using the QIAGEN QIAquick Gel Extraction Kit and Sanger sequencing was completed by Source Bioscience (Nottingham, England). The returned sequence (750 base pairs of cytb, Accession no: LR998983) was checked by eye, before a NCBI Nucleotide BLAST was conducted.

A maximum likelihood phylogeny was reconstructed using PhyML (Guindon et al 2010), with bootstrapping performed with 1000 replicates.

References

- Guindon S, Dufayard J F, Lefort V, Anisimova M, Hordijk W & Gascuel O 2010. New Algorithms and Methods to Estimate Maximum-Likelihood Phylogenies: Assessing the Performance of PhyML 3.0. *Systematic Biology* 59(3): 307-21.
- Helbig A J & Seibold I 1999. Molecular Phylogeny of Palearctic–African *Acrocephalus* and *Hippolais* Warblers (Aves: Sylviidae). *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution* 11(2): 246–260.

LE03.cytb:

TACTAGGCATTTGCCTAATTGTGCAAATCACCCACGGGTCTATTGCTAGCAATACATTACACAGCAGAC
ACTTCCCTAGCTTTCAGCTCCGTAGCCCATATCTGCCGAGACGTACAGTTCGGCTGACTAATTCGAAA
TCTCCATGCAAACGGAGCCTCATTTTTCTTTATTTGCATCTACCTACATATCGGCCGAGGGCTCTACTA
CGGCTCATAATAAATAAGAGACATGAAATGTTGGAATCATCCTACTCCTGATGCTAATAGCAACC
GCCTTTGTGGGATATGTCCTACCTTGAGGACAAATATCCTTCTGAGGGGCTACAGTTATCACTAACCT
CTTCTCAGCCATCCCTTACATTGGCCAAACACTAGTAGAATGAGCCTGAGGAGGATTCTCAGTCGAC
AACCCAACTCTCACTCGATTCTTCGCTCTCCACTTCCTCCTACCTTTCCTAATCGCGGGACTAACACTA
GTTACCTTACCTTCTACACGAAACAGGCTCAAACAACCTCTAGGTGTCCCATCAGACTGCGATAA
AATCCCATTCCACCCTTACTACTCCATCAAAGACATCCTAGGATTTGCCCTAATACTAATCCTACTAGC
CACTTTAGCACTATTTTTCCCCAAACATGCTAGGAGACCCAGAAAATTTTCGCGCCGGCCAACCCACTAG
CCACCCCTCCACACATCAAACCCGAATGATACTTCTATTTCGCATACGCGATTCTACGATCAATCCCCA